

converted to CaO at $\sim 850^\circ$. The complex $\text{Ca}(\text{acac})(\text{dbzm})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ loses the two water molecules at $\sim 200^\circ$ and is finally converted to CaO at $\sim 850^\circ$. In case of the complex $\text{Ca}(\text{bzac})(\text{dbzm})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$, the two water molecules appear to be weakly coordinated since these are lost at significantly lower temperature, just beyond 100° . After that the weight of the compound remains constant upto $\sim 200^\circ$ and then there is a gradual loss in weight and finally the complex gets converted to CaO at $\sim 950^\circ$.

Infrared spectra: The concerned ir absorption bands of mixed ligand complexes of Mg^{II} and Ca^{II} along with their assignments are recorded in Table 1. Appearance of strong absorption band at $\sim 1600-1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates the presence of coordinated C=O groups. In free salicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxyacetophenone bands at 1660 cm^{-1} and 1650 cm^{-1} respectively have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$. Bellamy and Beecher³ reported $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band at 1724 cm^{-1} in acetylacetone and benzoylacetone. The lowering of the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ in the mixed ligand complexes supports the coordination of the C=O groups to the metal atom. Bands at $420-450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are absent in the free ligands may be attributed to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ of M-O-C bonds. Weak bands at $220-300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be due to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ stretching of M-O-H bonds formed by the coordination of water molecule to the metal atom.

Nmr spectrum: ^1H nmr spectrum (DMSO- d_6 ; 90 MHz) of $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCHCOCH}_2]_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCHCOCH}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Mg}$ reveals complex multiplet at $\delta 7-8$ (ArH). In free benzoylacetone, the resonances due to the CH_2 and CH protons have been reported at $\delta 2.19$ and 6.18 respectively⁴, which are found shifted upfield ($\delta 1.66$ and 5.66) in this complex. In free dibenzolymethane, the signal due to the CH proton appears at $\delta 6.82$ which also shifted upfield ($\delta 6.40$ ppm) in the mixed ligand complex. Upfield shifts of these protons confirm the coordination of the C=O groups to the magnesium atom.

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Some Phenoxides and Mixed Phenoxy Derivatives of Antimony(III) : $[\text{SbCl}_{3-n}(\text{OAr})_n]$

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COMPARED to simple alkoxides, phenoxides of antimony(III) have received less attention^{1,2}. Although only some simple phenoxides of antimony(III) have been reported in the literature^{1,2}, yet little is known about the corresponding derivatives of sterically crowded aryloxy ligands. In the present communication we report the results on the synthesis and properties of some sterically crowded phenoxides and some mixed chlorophenoxide derivatives of antimony(III), $[\text{SbCl}_{3-n}(\text{OAr})_n]$.

Experimental

Antimony(III) chloride and phenols were distilled before use. All manipulations were carried out under strictly anhydrous conditions using dry solvents. Molecular weights of the derivatives were determined in benzene using a Gallenkamp ebulliometer. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra (CDCl_3 or CCl_4) on a JEOL FX 90 Q using TMS as external indicator.

Synthesis of $[\text{SbCl}_2(\text{OAr})]$: Freshly distilled antimony(III) chloride (3.24 g, 1.42 mmol) and 2,4,6-trimethylphenol (1.99 g, 1.46 mmol) were dissolved together in benzene (~ 80 ml). The contents were refluxed till the evolution of HCl gas ceased. The excess of solvent was then removed under reduced pressure to yield light pink crystals in quantitative yield (97%). The product was further purified by recrystallisation in n-hexane (Table 1).

Synthesis of $[\text{SbCl}(\text{OAr})_2]$: Potassium (1.07 g, 27.43 mmol) and 2,4,6-trimethylphenol (3.67 g, 26.98 mmol) were refluxed together (~ 3 h) in tetrahydrofuran (~ 20 ml) till a clear solution was obtained. The excess THF was removed and dried under reduced pressure. The potassium phenoxide was again dissolved in benzene and to it a freshly distilled SbCl_3 (3.13 g, 13.71 mmol) solution in benzene (~ 20 ml) was added. The contents were refluxed for another 1 h. After cooling, KCl formed during the reaction was filtered out and the excess solvent was removed from the filtrate under reduced pressure. A yellow solid product in quantitative yield (80%) was obtained (Table 1).

Synthesis of $[\text{Sb}(\text{OAr})_3]$: Sodium (0.36 g, 1.57 mmol) was taken together with 2,4,6-trimethylphenol (2.02 g, 1.49 mmol) in THF (~ 30 ml). The contents were refluxed till sodium was completely dissolved and a clear and transparent solution was obtained. THF was then completely removed under reduced pressure to give a solid. It was again redissolved in benzene, and SbCl_3 (1.13 g, 0.49 mmol)

TABLE 1—SYNTHESIS, ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF $[SbCl_{3-n}(OAr)_n]$

Sl. no.	SbCl ₃ g/ (mmol)	Ligand g/ (mmol)	K/Na g/ (mmol)	Product	Yield % (Nature)	Mol. wt. Found/ (Calcd.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
							Sb	Cl	O	H
1.	1.99 (8.72)	1.33 (9.87)	—	$[SbCl_2(-O-C_6H_4-)]$	96 (Golden yellow solid)	347 (342)	34.92 (35.63)	20.66 (20.78)	36.26 (35.12)	4.42 (3.80)
2.	1.02 (4.47)	1.99 (18.32)	0.32 (18.91)	$[Sb(-O-C_6H_4-)_3]$	99 (Yellow solid)	585 (569)	20.80 (22.41)	—	68.44 (68.29)	7.81 (6.86)
3.	4.75 (20.82)	2.54 (20.82)	0.81 (20.76)	$[SbCl_2(-O-C_6H_3-)]$	80 (Dark green viscous liquid)	335 (314)	38.09 (38.80)	22.03 (22.63)	—	—
4.	2.03 (8.89)	2.13 (17.87)	0.69 (17.84)	$[SbCl(-O-C_6H_3-)_2]$	96 (Brown sticky solid)	—	29.95 (30.49)	8.51 (8.88)	—	—
5.	1.22 (5.35)	2.00 (16.39)	0.63 (16.20)	$[Sb(-O-C_6H_3-)_3]$	89 (Yellow sticky solid)	522 (522)	23.92 (23.92)	—	56.74 (57.63)	4.96 (5.40)
6.	3.24 (14.20)	1.98 (14.56)	—	$[SbCl_2(-O-C_6H_2-)]$	97 (Brown solid)	—	36.47 (37.15)	22.10 (21.66)	33.20 (32.95)	4.38 (3.36)
7.	3.13 (13.72)	3.67 (26.98)	1.07 (27.43)	$[SbCl(-O-C_6H_2-)_2]$	80 (Yellow solid)	458 (427)	27.87 (28.49)	7.94 (8.29)	—	—
8.	1.13 (4.95)	2.02 (14.85)	0.36 (15.65)	$[Sb(-O-C_6H_2-)_3]$	96 (Yellow solid)	567 (527)	22.93 (23.11)	—	62.68 (61.51)	6.26 (6.39)
9.	5.75 (25.21)	3.45 (26.37)	0.98 (25.12)	$[SbCl_2(-O-C_6H-)]$	93 (Dark brown liquid)	355 (328)	36.97 (37.15)	20.91 (21.66)	—	—
10.	2.63 (11.53)	3.16 (23.24)	0.90 (23.07)	$[SbCl(-O-C_6H-)_2]$	85 (Brown solid)	456 (429)	27.67 (28.49)	7.88 (8.29)	—	—
11.	1.95 (8.55)	3.50 (25.74)	0.99 (25.88)	$[Sb(-O-C_6H-)_3]$	89 (Yellow solid)	541 (527)	22.54 (23.11)	—	—	—

in benzene (25 ml) was added to it. The contents were refluxed for about 12 h. The precipitated NaCl was filtered off and the excess solvent was removed from the filtrate. A yellow solid product was obtained in quantitative yield (96%). The product was further purified by recrystallisation in n-hexane (Table 1).

Similarly, other derivatives were prepared (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

Reactions of antimony(III) chloride with sterically substituted phenols in 1:1 molar ratio in dry benzene resulted in quantitative yield of the products. The contents were refluxed till the

evolution of HCl gas ceased completely,

Since the above reaction appears to be slow and takes many hours for the completion depending upon the nature of substitution in the phenyl ring, the following more convenient method has been used for the preparation of compounds of the type $[SbCl_{3-n}(OAr)_n]$ ($n = 1 - 3$). These derivatives have been prepared under strictly anhydrous conditions by the reactions of antimony(III) chloride with sodium or potassium phenoxides in 1:1, 1:2 and

NOTES

1 : 3 molar ratio in anhydrous benzene,

All these derivatives have been obtained in almost quantitative yields. These derivatives are sensitive to moisture and heat and are non-volatile even under reduced pressure. They are highly soluble in non-polar solvents. Some of the compounds have been purified by recrystallisation from a mixture of benzene and n-hexane.

Infrared¹ spectral data of $[SbCl_{3-n}(OAr)_n]$ are summarised in Table 2. The stretching OH bands at 3 680-3 560 cm^{-1} in free phenols were found missing in these phenoxy derivatives indicating the formation of the desired products². The bands appearing at 1 600-1 550 and 875-710 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu_{C=C}$ and out-of-plane ν_{CH} bending vibrations respectively^{2,3-5}. A number of bands observed at 1 180-910 and 600-500 cm^{-1} have been assigned to ν_{C-O} and ν_{Sb-O} respectively^{2,7,8}.

¹H nmr spectral data of these derivatives $[SbCl_{3-n}(OAr)_n]$ have also been recorded at room temperature (Table 2). In case of $[SbCl_2(-O-\text{C}_6H_4-)]$,

the substituted methyl and aromatic protons appear at δ 2.19 and 6.84-7.04 ppm respectively. Except that the respective methyl protons on the benzene nucleus which undergo slight upfield chemical shift, there appears to be little change in the position of aromatic signals as compared to the free ligand 2,6-dimethylphenol. In case of all other derivatives, the same pattern of chemical shifts has been observed as described above. In bis-phenoxy derivatives of antimony(III) of the type $[SbCl(OAr)_2]$, the methyl substituted and aromatic protons appear at δ 2.23 and 6.95-6.75 ppm respectively. Compared to $[SbCl_2(OAr)]$, the methyl and aromatic protons show downfield shifts in derivatives of the type $[SbCl(OAr)_2]$. The same trends of chemical shifts continue in the case of tris-derivatives $[Sb(OAr)_3]$. The integration ratio in all these products corresponds to the number of chemically different types of protons.

As all these compounds are monomeric in refluxing benzene and exhibit only one type of ¹H nmr signal for aryloxy groups, it may be assumed that the geometry around antimony atom is tetrahedral with one of the positions occupied by a stereo chemically active lone pair of electrons,

where, X = ArO or Cl.

TABLE 2—IR (cm^{-1})^a AND ¹H NMR^b SPECTRAL DATA OF $[SbCl_{3-n}(OAr)_n]$

Sl. no.†	$\nu_{C=C}$	ν_{C-O}	ν_{Sb-O}	Methyl/t-Butyl proton ^{**}	ArH
1.	1 580br	1 700br, 1 070br, 1 000s, 930w	550s, 500m	1.06(br) ^a	6.49-7.06(m)
2.	1 590br	1 090br, 960br	540br	1.80(s) ^b	6.75-7.29(m)
3.	1 575m	1 160m, 1 085vs, 1 025br, 1 005m, 940m	500s, 555m, 520m, 590br	2.19(s) ^b	6.84-7.04(m)
4.	1 575m	1 150s, 1 070s, 1 020br, 980m, 950br, 900s	590br	2.23(br) ^b	6.75-6.95(m)
5.	1 595s	1 160m, 1 070s, 1 030br, 990m, 915s	500br	2.15(br) ^b	6.62-6.84(m)
6.	—	1 160m, 1 030br, 980br, 930br	580br	2.02(s) ^b	6.70(br)
7.	1 600br	1 185vs, 1 145br, 1 005br, 970br, 920m	575br	2.11(br) ^a	6.62(s)
8.	1 590br	1 185s, 1 140m, 1 000br, 950br, 910br	570br	2.23(s) ^a	6.84(s)
9.	1 575br	1 160w, 1 085vs, 1 025br, 1 005s, 940m	555m, 520m	2.07(d) ^b	6.92-7.21(m)
10.	1 550br	1 160br, 1 060br, 1 000br, 975br, 915br	570br, 530br	2.12(br) ^b	6.38-6.66(m)
11.	1 590br, 1 555m	1 180br, 1 145br, 1 070s, 1 010br, 985m, 925m	580br	2.08(br) ^b	6.42-6.64(m)
12.	2,6-Dimethylphenol			2.22(s) ^b	6.54-7.09(m)
13.	2,4,6-Trimethylphenol			2.22(s) ^b	6.93(s)
14.	2,6,8-Trimethylphenol			2.19(d) ^b	6.70-6.89(m)

^abr=broad, m=medium, s=strong, vs=very strong, w=weak, vw=very weak. ^b Solvent: ^cCCl₄, ^dODCl₃, s=singlet, d=doublet, br=broad, m=multiplet. †Corresponds to the compounds in Table 1.

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Some Macrocyclic Complexes of Oxometal Ions. Part-I. Studies on some Oxozirconium(IV) Complexes

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In previous communications, we reported several transition metal complexes of different macrocyclic ligands¹⁻⁵. We now report the synthesis and characterisation of some oxozirconium(IV) complexes with two new 14-membered N₄-donor macro-

cycles, viz. dibenzo[e,f]-2,3,9,10-tetraphenyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-1,3,8,10-tetraene (L₁) and 1,4,8,11-tetradeca-2,3,9,10-dibenzocyclotetradeca-5,7,12,14-tetraene (L₂). All the complexes possess 1 : 1 stoichiometry, [ZrO(L)]X₂, where, L=L₁ or L₂; X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, ClO₄⁻, BF₄⁻ and 1/2 C₂O₄²⁻.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by initially refluxing the oxozirconium(IV) chloride (0.001 mol, 0.322 g) with *o*- or *m*-phenylenediamine (0.002 mol, 0.216 g) in methanol (50 ml) for 4 h. To it was then added benzil (0.002 mol, 0.420 g) for ligand L₁ and acetylacetone (0.002 mol, 0.200 ml) for ligand L₂ and further refluxed for 10–16 h. The resulting dark brown solution was purified by tlc and the complexes were crystallised from the light brown fraction using petroleum ether.

For preparing the complexes of other anions, oxozirconium(IV) chloride (0.001 mol, 0.322 g) was suspended in methanol (50 ml) and treated with silver perchlorate (nitrate/tetrafluoroborate) or ammonium thiocyanate (oxalate) (0.002 mol) and stirred for 4 h. The silver or ammonium chlorides so formed were filtered out and the resulting solution was treated as outlined above. The resulting dark brown complexes were filtered and dried. The complexes were characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance, molecular weight, ir and ¹H nmr spectral data (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis shows that in case of all the complexes only one mole of the tetradentate macrocycle, obtained by the template condensation

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Mol. wt. Found/Calcd.	Molar conductance* ^c Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹
	Zr	O	H	N		
[ZrO(L ₁)](ClO ₄) ₂	10.88 (10.46)	— (55.17)	— (8.22)	— (8.64)	870 (868)	68.5 ^a
[ZrO(L ₁)](NO ₃) ₂	11.02 (11.45)	60.61 (60.88)	8.87 (8.52)	10.87 (10.57)	790 (795)	178 ^b
[ZrO(L ₁)](BF ₄) ₂	10.45 (10.79)	— (59.94)	— (8.82)	— (11.59)	828 (849)	178 ^b
[ZrO(L ₁)](Cl) ₂	12.90 (12.26)	64.88 (64.69)	8.87 (8.71)	7.86 (7.55)	788 (742)	169.1 ^b
[ZrO(L ₂)](SCN) ₂	11.08 (11.56)	69.52 (64.04)	8.78 (8.56)	10.48 (10.67)	789 (787)	167.4 ^b
[ZrO(L ₂)](C ₂ O ₄)	10.08 (10.74)	68.08 (63.84)	8.58 (8.81)	8.25 (6.61)	858 (847)	57.3 ^c
[ZrO(L ₂)](ClO ₄) ₂	14.55 (14.00)	— (40.62)	— (8.89)	— (8.62)	655 (650)	75.2 ^c
[ZrO(L ₂)](NO ₃) ₂	15.26 (15.88)	45.21 (45.91)	4.85 (4.17)	14.04 (14.61)	575 (576)	52.8 ^a
[ZrO(L ₂)](BF ₄) ₂	14.86 (14.61)	— (42.88)	— (8.85)	8.70 (8.99)	828 (828)	186 ^d
[ZrO(L ₂)](Cl) ₂	17.95 (17.48)	51.04 (50.58)	4.24 (4.59)	20.84 (20.78)	528 (522)	180 ^d
[ZrO(L ₂)](SCN) ₂	15.68 (16.05)	50.14 (50.74)	4.81 (4.28)	14.28 (14.82)	571 (567)	164.8 ^d
[ZrO(L ₂)](C ₂ O ₄)	14.25 (14.99)	47.87 (47.45)	8.65 (8.95)	9.83 (9.29)	614 (627)	178.8 ^d

*L₁ = C₂₀H₂₀N₄; L₂ = C₂₂H₂₂N₄. **In ^aEtOH, ^bMeOH, ^cDMSO, ^dacetone.